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ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN AND UZBEKISTAN EXPERIENCE OF REGULATING REAL ESTATE ACTIVITIES

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***Abstract:** This article analyzes the foreign and Uzbek experience in regulating real estate activities. Three types of models are proposed that allow us to identify the strengths and weaknesses of real estate regulation in different countries: hard, medium and soft. According to the author, based on empirical data from different countries, the most effective model of regulating real estate activities is the hard model, which ensures a high level of quality of services provided due to high requirements and regulation by both the state and the professional community.*

***Keywords:** real estate, real estate market, real estate disposal, residential and non-residential premises, real estate activities, realtor, model of regulation of real estate activities, real estate, agent.*

Introduction

As a result of the socio-economic reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan, the demopolization, denationalization and privatization of state property, a class of private owners, including real estate owners, has emerged in the country. Today, they can not only use and own this real estate, but also dispose of it. The development of commodity-money relations in the country, the formation of a multi-level economy, has led to the emergence of essentially new markets, such as the commodity exchange, money and credit market, securities, and various services markets. Among these types of markets, the real estate market occupies a special place, that is, it is the central link in the entire system of market relations.

Although the Law "On Real Estate Activities" was adopted in our country on December 22, 2010, and the National Standard of Real Estate Services (No. 1) "General Requirements for Internal Regulations for Quality Control of Real Estate Services" was adopted on July 12, 2011, Since the real estate and real estate business of Uzbekistan is quite "young" compared to the real estate business of not only Western, but also developing countries, special attention should be paid to studying effective mechanisms for regulating foreign real estate activities and the possibilities of their practical application in Uzbekistan. The potential for improving the quality of self-

regulation in Uzbekistan is not exhausted, which will allow in the near future to introduce mechanisms that will raise the quality of real estate services to the level of the best analogues in the world.

A realtor is a person who provides intermediary services in the real estate market. The term "realtor" appeared in the USA in 1916 and was registered as a special designation of the Association of Realtors. Currently, realtors abroad are mainly engaged in mediation in the purchase and sale of real estate. Real estate activity is an entrepreneurial activity in the real estate market carried out by independent individuals who organize transactions (sale, purchase, exchange, rent, mortgage, leasing) with real estate and rights to it (buildings, structures, residential and non-residential premises, land plots). The main goal of this activity is to make a profit.

Real estate activities may also include brokerage and agency activities, property management, attracting private investment in the creation and development of real estate, transferring residential buildings to non-residential areas, and reconstructing and redeveloping buildings.

Literature review

Having studied the problematic aspects and relevance of the topic and cited them in their scientific research and studies, scientists from the CIS countries, such as VA Shanyukevich et al., studied the theoretical and practical aspects of real estate activity in their work "Fundamentals of Real Estate Activity" [1], while GV Fedotov and BA Volkov conducted research in the field of real estate, real estate and development activities in their textbooks "Economics of Real Estate" [2] and MA Kotlyarov, Dzh. Drain, AB Bril et al. conducted research in the field of real estate, real estate and development activities in their monographs "Development of Real Estate" [3]. We can also cite domestic scientists such as Sh. Shohazami, who developed models of real estate activity and development concepts for regulating and coordinating real estate activity in his textbook "Real Estate Activity" [4], and A. Kravchenko, V. Yodgorov, and others who studied real estate and real estate activity.

Research Methodology

During the research process Real estate activity and its regulation The work of foreign and domestic scientists on the features of international practice in the field of economic development and their role in the economy was studied and analyzed. The article effectively used methods such as theoretical observation, systematic approach, observation, generalization, analysis, synthesis, as well as Real estate activity and its regulation Conclusions and suggestions have been formulated regarding the problems and their solutions.

Analysis and results

The United States is one of the oldest real estate markets in the world. The term "Realtor" itself appeared in the United States in 1916 and became the official trademark of the National Association of Realtors (NAR). Only NARA person who is licensed to use the trademark and is a member of the country's National Association of Realtors may be called a realtor, otherwise the profession is called a real estate agent. The terms "realtor" and "real estate agent" refer to the performance of the same functions, but the status of a realtor is higher, as additional requirements are imposed on him, which increases the quality of service and the level of trust of clients.

The real estate market and real estate services are of great importance to the US national economy, are the driving force behind the development of many related industries, and are also one of the main national ideas - "Every American has their own home!" The prestige of the profession and NAR The association's influence is so great that even the President of the United States attends the association's annual conference in Washington.

In the USA, the relationship between a realtor and a client is strictly regulated by law and is set out in special rules (Agency Law). In addition to legal regulation, compliance with the Code of Ethics is also mandatory. For the Western world, the Code of Ethics is not just a set of recommended rules, but also strictly regulated guidelines for the conduct of real estate activities, which are as mandatory as compliance with the laws of the country. NAR The code of ethics is based on principles organized in the form of an acronym (OLD CAR), with each letter representing one of the 6 basic principles [5] (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Principles of conducting real estate activities in the USA (OLD CAR)*

Source: compiled by the author based on information from the official website of the National Association of Realtors USA (NAR), [www](http://www.nar.org).

A candidate who wants to become a realtor must study and pass a series of tests before being able to adhere to the code of ethics and confirm compliance with the high standards of the real estate profession. High requirements are imposed on the candidate's moral qualities, primarily the absence of a criminal record, for which the US Department of Real Estate thoroughly studies the questionnaire and checks its accuracy through government databases.

The next step is for the candidate to complete 45 to 180 hours of specialized training (depending on the state), then take an exam to determine the legal and professional background of the school [6]. After that, the candidate must take a more difficult test - an exam at the state real estate department; if successfully passed, the candidate receives a license. Most states require continuing education every two years. It is also important that the license issued is valid only in the state in which it was obtained.

Next, a realtor must join a self-regulatory organization, insure his professional activities and work for 2-3 years in a real estate company. Only after that he can start his own business. A big competitive advantage of joining the NAR is access to a single real estate database (MLS - multilisting system), which is accessible only to realtors who are members of the association.

In the United States, real estate is a prestigious and highly paid profession, the success of which is based on a high level of qualification, a long-standing reputation as a specialist, and strict adherence to the law and a code of ethics. The main task of a real estate agent is mediation, which consists of searching, selecting properties, negotiating, collecting documents and closing the transaction. The "purity" of the transaction is checked by the real estate firm or lawyers of each party, a notary checks the completeness and certifies the signatures.

In France, real estate activities are divided into three areas: buying and selling, renting and property management. There is a separate license for each area. Mandatory requirements for the candidate are the absence of a criminal record, a state diploma with a minimum of three years of study in the field of "Law", economics, real estate, a license issued by the local prefecture (carte professionnelle – professional card), as well as mandatory professional insurance [7]. The role of a real estate agent in France is mediation. The guarantor of the "purity" of the transaction is a notary who has full

access to information about all possible situations in real estate.

In Germany, the trademark "realtor" is not used, which requires maintaining a high standard of service quality, and the term "real estate agent" (Immobilienmakler) is used instead. The main requirements for a real estate agent in Germany are a clean criminal record and a license from the Chamber of Commerce and Industry [8, Immobilienverband Deutschland (IVD), [www](#)].

There are no requirements for educational level, mandatory professional liability insurance, and membership in the national real estate association (Immobilienverband Deutschland, IVD) and they are voluntary, which leads to a decline in the quality of services and the reputation of the profession.

Professional agents voluntarily undergo specialized training and join a national real estate association, which is an important competitive advantage in the eyes of clients. The legality of the transaction is confirmed by a notary, who guarantees the "purity" of the transaction.

The UK has one of the highest property prices in the world, making the agency industry very popular. The industry is regulated by the Estate Agents Acts of 1979, 2007, 2012, etc., and is overseen by self-regulatory bodies such as The Independent Network of Estate Agents (INEA) and the National Association of Estate Agents (NAEA) [9, The Independent Network of Estate Agents (INEA). [www](#)]. It is important to note that there are no requirements for real estate agents to be qualified, licensed, have a criminal record or be a member of a self-regulatory body, so the quality of services and consumer confidence in them varies from one agency to another.

In Spain, there are no special requirements for real estate agents, they prepare the documents, including checking their "purity", after which the documents are handed over to a notary who takes on great responsibility and, if there is the slightest doubt about the documents, he refuses to conclude the transaction. Insurance of the real estate agent's professional activities is not mandatory and is carried out on a voluntary basis. The exception is Catalonia, where real estate agents are required to undergo training and register in a specialized register [10, La Asociación Profesional de Administradores y Agentes Inmobiliarios (APAGI), [www](#)].

There is no special state regulation of real estate activities in Russia. In 2002, mandatory licensing was abolished, and draft laws regulating this activity were repeatedly rejected. In 1992, a national association of professional participants in the real estate market, the Russian Guild of Realtors (RGR), was created, which performs self-regulatory functions. Today, its influence on the market is not significant, since membership in the RGR is voluntary. According to the National Agency for Financial

Research - NAFI, this is not an indicator of the quality of the services provided.

By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6044 dated August 24, 2020, the mandatory licensing procedure for real estate activities in Uzbekistan was abolished. Instead, membership in the Association of Real Estate Organizations of Uzbekistan (RTU), a national association of professional participants in the real estate market that performs self-regulatory functions, was made mandatory. Also, registration as a business entity, The introduction of a Unified Multilisting System (electronic platform for the real estate market) in the sector and the expansion of activities It was determined that it would be implemented based on a qualification certificate.

The Benelux countries - the Netherlands, Belgium and Luxembourg - have one of the most stringent models of agency regulation. This model combines a high proportion of state and professional-public regulation, since not only mandatory licensing is regulated, but also mandatory membership in a self-regulatory organization (Institut Professionnel des Agents Immobiliers - IPI). In this case, each agent is assigned a personal identification code, which is recorded in all documents, including the contract with the client. Joining the national association of real estate agents is accompanied by three years of study, passing exams and obtaining a diploma for agency work, followed by an internship with an experienced broker [11, Institut Professionnel des Agents Immobiliers (IPI), www].

Having studied the features of the regulation of real estate (agency) activities in different countries, we present their main distinguishing features (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparison of models of regulating real estate activities in different countries*

	USA	France	Germany	Great Britain	Russia	Uzbekistan	Spain	Benelux countries
1. RF regulation model	Solid model	Solid model	Medium model	Medium model	Soft model	Medium model	Soft model	Solid model
2. National Association	NAR	FNAIM	IVD	INEA	RGR	RTU	APAGI	IPI
3. Licensing	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+
4. Insurance	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	+
5. No criminal record	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+
6. Regulation based on	high	high	middle	middle	low	middle	low	high

legislation								
7. Professional reputation	high	middle	middle	middle	low	middle	low	high

Source: compiled by the author.

Based on the above, it can be noted that real estate (agency) activities are regulated differently in different countries, therefore, depending on the degree of regulation of this activity, three types of models can be distinguished: hard, medium and soft model (Figure 2).

Models of regulating real estate (agency) activities:

- a strict model of regulation of real estate activities - a high level of regulation by the state and the professional community, high requirements for real estate agents, high-quality services with minimal risk for the client;
- average model of regulation of real estate activities - partial regulation by the state and the professional community, minimum requirements for real estate agents, differentiated quality of services with minimal risks for the client;
- soft model of regulation of real estate activities - low level of regulation by the state and the professional community, lack of significant requirements for realtors, differentiated quality of services with an average level of risk for the client.

In conclusion, based on empirical data from different countries, we believe that the most effective model is a strict model of real estate regulation, which ensures a high level of stability in the quality of services provided due to high requirements and regulation by both the state and the professional community.

Figure 2. Models of regulating real estate activities*

Source: compiled by the author.

Professional associations of real estate agents in Europe and the United States are seeking to increase the impact of self-regulation of real estate activities in order to improve the quality of professional activities. Figure 2 shows the levels of global self-regulation of real estate activities.

Self-regulation of real estate activities consists of five levels. At the global level – the International Real Estate Federation (FIABCI), this federation summarizes the best practices of the world, organizes international conferences for the exchange of experience and develops methodological materials. This federation has been a unifying link for real estate market specialists around the world since 1951, without administrative control. The International Real Estate Federation includes 70 countries, 90 national associations, more than 40 real estate specialists and more than 1 million association members [12, International Real Estate Federation (FIAVSI), www].

At the European level, the European Association of Real Estate Professions (CEPI) is an international non-profit organization founded in Brussels in 1990. It unites national associations of professionals from 19 countries in the European Union, thereby increasing the confidence of clients in their brand [13, European Association of Real Estate Professions (SEPI), www]. The goal of the association is to develop the real estate services market by expanding internal and external relations, organizing research projects, and training future real estate professionals.

The international level (National Association of Realtors – NAR) is available to countries whose national associations use the "realtor" trademark, obliging these associations to gradually pursue a policy of transition to high quality standards of real estate services.

Figure 3. Self-regulation of real estate activities*

Source: compiled by the author.

At the national level, each country has its own associations of real estate professionals. In Uzbekistan, such an association, as mentioned above, is the Uzbekistan Association of Real Estate Organizations, established in 2012, which unites 267 real estate organizations from different regions of our republic (data as of the beginning of 2026). The main tasks of the association are: presenting the “realtor” trademark, creating professional standards and a code of ethics for realtors, interacting with government agencies, participating in the formation of the regulatory framework, training personnel, etc.

Conclusion/Recommendations

Thus, we can, summarizing world experience, distinguish three models of regulation of real estate activities: hard, medium and soft. Since the real estate and real estate business of Uzbekistan is quite "young" compared to the real estate business not only of the West, but also of developing countries, special attention should be paid to studying effective mechanisms for regulating real estate activities abroad and the possibilities of their practical application in Uzbekistan. It should be noted that the potential for improving the quality of self-regulation in Uzbekistan is inexhaustible, and this will allow in the near future to introduce mechanisms that will raise the quality of real estate services to the level of the best world analogues.

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